

Performance Index for Optimizing Sensor Fault Detection of a Class of Nonlinear Systems

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Abstract: This paper develops a performance index that can be used to find the optimal design parameters of the observer-based residual generator and adaptive threshold of a fault detection scheme for a class of nonlinear systems. The performance of the fault detection scheme is analyzed with respect to the fault detectability of incipient sensor faults, which depends on the dynamic behavior of the residual and the adaptive threshold generator. The proposed performance index is based on the distance between two limit sets that are guaranteed to include the residual under fault-free and faulty conditions. The novelty of this distance metric stems from the parametrization of the limit sets in relation to (i) the design parameters of both the residual generator and adaptive threshold, (ii) the bounds on the system disturbances and measurement noise, and (iii) the fault function and evolution rate. An optimization problem is formulated for finding the design parameters of the fault detection scheme such that the set of guaranteed strongly detectable faults is maximized, where this set is defined based on the distance between the separated fault-free and faulty limit set.

Keywords: Detectability analysis, fault detection, sensor faults, nonlinear systems, residual generator, adaptive threshold, observer

1. INTRODUCTION

Fault detection (FD) is the primary step before any action towards handling a faulty situation. To guarantee the good performance of an FD process, quantitative detectability requirements should be fulfilled, including the number of false alarms, the number of missed detections and the time of fault detection (Odgaard et al., 2013; Goupil et al., 2015). One way to check the fulfillment of these requirements is by testing the FD scheme through Monte Carlo studies simulating different modeling uncertainties (system disturbances, measurement noise etc) and fault characteristics (type, evolution rate, magnitude etc) (Odgaard et al., 2013). Another way is by performing a formal fault detectability analysis, leading to mathematical conditions that are functions of any modeling uncertainty and faults that satisfy specific assumptions (Polycarpou and Trunov, 2000; Nyberg, 2002). While the simulation-based approach can be applied to any FD scheme, fault detectability analysis can be realized in model-based FD methods. However, fault detectability analysis methods are systematic and their analytical results can be used not only for evaluating an FD scheme (Xing and Xia, 2017) but also for optimizing its design (Harirchi et al., 2016; Reppa et al., 2017).

There are two ways to characterize fault detectability: (i) as a property of the system (called *system-based* here after) (Basseville, 1999; Del Gobbo and Napolitano, 2000; Staroswiecki

and Comtet-Varga, 2001; Nyberg, 2002; Nyberg and Frisk, 2006; Eriksson et al., 2013), Ch. 5 in (Blanke et al., 2016), Ch. 4 in (Ding, 2013), and (ii) as a property of the designed FD scheme (called *FD-based* here after) (Chen and Patton, 1999; Basseville, 1999; Polycarpou and Trunov, 2000; Zhang et al., 2008; Kodakkadan et al., 2017; Reppa et al., 2016, 2015), Ch. 6 in (Blanke et al., 2016). While in the case of linear systems there are many tools to analyze system- and FD-based detectability (Chen and Patton, 1999; Del Gobbo and Napolitano, 2000; Nyberg, 2002; Ding, 2013; Kodakkadan et al., 2017), this is not the same in the case of nonlinear systems.

Irrespective of its type (system-based or FD-based) and the domain of analysis, the goal of the fault detectability analysis is to specify if an individual fault is weakly or strongly detectable, or non-detectable in any case. The weak fault detectability is commonly associated with the transient behavior of the system or the FD scheme after the occurrence of the fault, and depends on time (Chen and Patton, 1994; Polycarpou and Trunov, 2000; Nyberg, 2002; Reppa et al., 2016). The effects of a weakly detectable fault are disclosed for a finite time interval (if exists). On the contrary, strong fault detectability is linked to the asymptotic behavior of the system or the FD scheme after the occurrence of the fault (Chen and Patton, 1994; Nyberg, 2002). The effects of a strongly detectable fault that is persistently non-zero (e.g. bias fault) do not vanish with time (Chen and Patton, 1999; Varga, 2017). At last, non-detectability implies that there is no time instant at which the effects of a fault can be captured (Staroswiecki and Comtet-Varga, 2001; Kodakkadan et al., 2015).

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Both weak and strong detectability analysis are important. In several real systems (e.g. industrial processes) there may be faults that are weakly detectable without being strongly detectable (see the references herein (Nyberg, 2002)). Moreover, since weak detectability is related to the transient behavior of the system, it is related to the detection time. A small detection delay plays a key role in activating the remedial actions in a fault tolerant control scheme fast (Kinnaert et al., 2001). However, if a fault is incipient, then it can be very difficult to detect this fault in a transient period (Chen and Patton, 1994), unless it is strongly detectable. For this reason, strong fault detectability can be a reliable metric to evaluate the performance of an FD scheme in detecting incipient faults. However, there are very few existing results of strong fault detectability analysis that consider time-varying faults (i.e. not constant faults) (Reppa et al., 2015, 2017), but without considering explicitly the evolution rate of a fault after its occurrence.

The goal of this work is the design of a performance index, which can be used to find the optimal design parameters of the observer-based residual generator and the adaptive threshold generator of an FD scheme for a class of nonlinear systems. The main contribution is that the performance of the FD scheme is analyzed with respect to the strongly detectable time-varying sensor faults, which may evolve slowly. We first design an FD scheme, assuming partial-state measurements and bounded system disturbances and measurement noise. A fault is detected when the residual vector is not included in a time-varying convex set, defined by the generated adaptive thresholds. The methodology for designing the performance index is based on: (i) the ultimate bound set and robust positively invariant (RPI) set of the state estimation error, and (ii) the computation of the limit sets (projections of the ultimate bounds and RPI sets) within which the residual vector converges. These limit sets are parametrized with respect to (i) the design parameters of both the residual generator and adaptive threshold, which are the eigenvalues and eigenvectors of the observer (ii) the bounds on the system disturbances and measurement noise, and (iii) the fault function and temporal evolution rate. The distance between the limit sets under fault-free and faulty conditions is a metric of their separation, which guarantees sensor fault detectability. The distance between the separated sets is used to define the set of guaranteed strongly detectable faults. Then, we formulate an optimization problem for finding the design parameters of the observer and adaptive threshold, aiming at maximizing the set of strongly detectable faults.

This paper extends the preliminary results in (Reppa et al., 2017) by: (i) relaxing the assumption of full-state measurements, (ii) obtaining new results on strong detectability of incipient faults, and (iii) improving the optimization formulation that generalizes the set of strongly detectable sensor faults.

This paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents the problem formulation, followed by Section 3 that describes the design of the observer-based FD scheme. The methodology for designing the performance index and the formulation of the optimization problem of the FD scheme are illustrated in Section 4, followed by some concluding remarks in Section 5.

Notation: The symbols \preceq, \succeq signify the element-wise inequalities, $|\cdot|$ denotes the element-wise absolute value (matrix modulus function), \oplus symbolizes the Minkowski sum of sets, and $\|\cdot\|$ denotes a norm.

2. PROBLEM FORMULATION

We consider the class of nonlinear uncertain systems

$$\dot{x}(t) = Ax(t) + \gamma(Cx(t), u(t)) + \eta(t) \quad (1)$$

$$y(t) = Cx(t) + d(t) + f(t) \quad (2)$$

where $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the state vector, $u \in \mathbb{R}^\ell$ is the input vector, $y \in \mathbb{R}^m$ is the output vector, $A \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ is a matrix representing the linearized part of the state equation, $\gamma: \mathbb{R}^m \times \mathbb{R}^\ell \mapsto \mathbb{R}^n$ characterizes the nonlinear part of system dynamics and $C \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$ is the output matrix. Moreover, $\eta \in \mathbb{R}^n$ models unknown additive disturbances, $d \in \mathbb{R}^m$ is the sensor noise and $f \in \mathbb{R}^m$ represents the permanent change in the output y due to a single fault in sensor i ; i.e.

$$f(t) = \mathbb{F}^{(i)} f_i(t) \quad (3)$$

$$f_i(t) = \begin{cases} 0, & t < T_i \\ (1 - e^{-\alpha_i(t-T_i)}) \varphi_i(t - T_i) & t \geq T_i \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

$$\mathbb{F}^{(i)} = \underbrace{[0, \dots, 0]_{i-1}}_{i-1}, \underbrace{[1, 0, \dots, 0]_{m-i}}_{m-i}^\top \quad (5)$$

where $\alpha_i \in \mathbb{R}$ models the evolution rate with $\alpha_i > 0$, $T_i \in \mathbb{R}$ is the time of occurrence, $\varphi_i \in \mathbb{R}$ is the fault function with $\varphi_i(t) \neq 0$ for all $t \geq 0$, and $\mathbb{F}^{(i)}$ denotes which of the sensors is faulty. The nonlinear system (1) is monitored by m sensors ($m \leq n$) characterized by the output vector y , where each sensor measures one state, implying that each row of $C \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$ contains one non-zero element that equals to one.

The objective of this work is to design a performance index for an observer-based fault detection scheme, which can be used for its optimization aiming at ensuring the detectability of the sensor fault f_i , described by (4), for all $i \in \{1, \dots, m\}$, taking into account the following assumptions:

Assumption 1: The state vector $x(t)$ and input vector $u(t)$ generated by a feedback controller remain uniformly bounded before and after the occurrence of a sensor fault; i.e., there exist a compact region of stability $\mathcal{X} \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ and admissible control inputs $u \in \mathcal{U}$ with \mathcal{U} compact in \mathbb{R}^ℓ such that $(x(t), u(t)) \in \mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{U}$, for all $t \geq 0$.

Assumption 2: The nonlinear function $\gamma_j \in \mathbb{R}$, $j \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ is locally Lipschitz on Cx and for any $u \in \mathcal{U}$ and $t \geq 0$, and the pair (C, A) is observable.

Assumption 3: The system disturbance η and the measurement noise d are uniformly bounded; i.e., $|\eta(t)| \preceq \bar{\eta}$, $|d(t)| \preceq \bar{d}$, where $\bar{\eta}, \bar{d} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ are known vector bounds.

Assumption 4: The sensor fault vector f is unknown but uniformly bounded; i.e., $|f(t)| \prec \infty$.

3. OBSERVER-BASED FAULT DETECTION SCHEME

The proposed observer-based fault detection scheme consists of: (i) the residual generator, (ii) the adaptive threshold generator, (iii) the residual evaluation and (iii) the decision logic.

3.1 Residual Generator

The residual vector is expressed as

$$\varepsilon_y(t) = y(t) - C\hat{x}(t), \quad (6)$$

$$\dot{\hat{x}}(t) = (A - LC)\hat{x}(t) + \gamma(y(t), u(t)) + Ly(t) \quad (7)$$

where $\hat{x} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the estimation of x ($\hat{x}(0) \in \mathcal{X}$) and $L \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times m}$ is the observer gain matrix chosen such that $A - LC$ is stable. Let us define the diagonalizable form of $A - LC$ as

$$A - LC = V\Lambda V^{-1} \quad (8)$$

where Λ is a diagonal matrix containing real, negative eigenvalues and V is a matrix comprised of the eigenvectors of $A - LC$. By definition C has linearly independent rows, implying that there exists its unique right inverse denoted by C^+ with $C^+ = C^T(CC^T)^{-1}$. Since each sensor measures one state, the rows of C , denoted as C_i , $i \in \{1, \dots, m\}$, are orthonormal; therefore $C_i C_j^T = 1$ if $i = j$ and $C_i C_j^T = 0$ if $i \neq j$, leading to $(CC^T) = I$ and $CC^+ = I$, $C^+ = C^T$. Thus, the observer gain can be parameterized as

$$L = LCC^T = (A - V\Lambda V^{-1})C^T \quad (9)$$

Assuming no faults (i.e. fault-free conditions), we define

$$y_H = Cx + d \quad (10)$$

$$\dot{\hat{x}}_H = V\Lambda V^{-1}\hat{x}_H + \gamma(y_H, u) + Ly_H, \quad (11)$$

$$\varepsilon_{x_H} = x - \hat{x}_H \quad (12)$$

$$\varepsilon_{y_H} = y_H - C\hat{x}_H = C\varepsilon_{x_H} + d \quad (13)$$

Based on (1), (8), (9) and (11), ε_{x_H} defined in (12) satisfies

$$V^{-1}\dot{\varepsilon}_{x_H}(t) = \Lambda V^{-1}\varepsilon_{x_H}(t) + z(t) \quad (14)$$

$$z = V^{-1}(\gamma(Cx, u) - \gamma(y_H, u) + \eta) + (\Lambda V^{-1} - V^{-1}A)C^T d \quad (15)$$

Solving (14) yields

$$V^{-1}\varepsilon_{x_H} = e^{\Lambda t}V^{-1}\varepsilon_{x_H}(0) + \int_0^t e^{\Lambda(t-\tau)}z(\tau)d\tau \quad (16)$$

Assumption 2 implies

$$|\gamma(Cx, u) - \gamma(y_H, u)| \leq \Gamma \|\bar{d}\| \quad (17)$$

$$\Gamma = [\lambda_{\gamma_1} \dots \lambda_{\gamma_n}]^T \quad (18)$$

where λ_{γ_j} , $j \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ is the Lipschitz constant related to γ_j (see Assumption 2). Based on (17) and Assumption 3, z in (15) satisfies

$$|z| \leq -\Lambda\chi_H \quad (19)$$

$$\chi_H = -\Lambda^{-1}(|V^{-1}|(\Gamma\|\bar{d}\| + \bar{\eta}) + |\Lambda V^{-1} - V^{-1}A|C^T\bar{d}) \quad (20)$$

Let us define $\bar{x} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ the bound such that $|\varepsilon_{x_H}(0)| \leq \bar{x}$ (see Assumption 1); then, given (16), a bound on $|V^{-1}\varepsilon_{x_H}|$ satisfies

$$|V^{-1}\varepsilon_{x_H}(t)| \leq E(t) \quad (21)$$

$$E(t) = e^{\Lambda t}|V^{-1}|\bar{x} + (I - e^{\Lambda t})\chi_H \quad (22)$$

3.2 Adaptive Threshold Generator & Residual Evaluation

The adaptive threshold is designed to bound the residual assuming fault-free conditions. Equation (13) can be equivalently written as $\varepsilon_{y_H} = CVV^{-1}\varepsilon_{x_H} + d$. Based on (21) and Assumption 3, the adaptive threshold denoted by $\bar{\varepsilon}_y(t)$ is defined as

$$|\varepsilon_{y_H}(t)| \leq C|V||V^{-1}\varepsilon_{x_H}(t)| + |d(t)| \leq \bar{\varepsilon}_y(t) \quad (23)$$

$$\bar{\varepsilon}_y(t) = C|V|E(t) + \bar{d} \quad (24)$$

Equations (21) and (22) imply that ε_{x_H} is *uniformly bounded*; i.e

$$\varepsilon_{x_H}(t) \in \Omega_H(t), \forall t \quad (25)$$

$$\Omega_H(t) = \{\varepsilon \in \mathbb{R}^n : |V^{-1}\varepsilon| \leq E(t)\} \quad (26)$$

As $t \rightarrow \infty$, $\limsup_{t \rightarrow \infty} E(t) = \chi_H$ and $\Omega_H(t)$ converges to the minimal ultimate bound set, denoted by $\Omega_H(\infty)$ and defined as

$$\Omega_H(\infty) = \{\varepsilon \in \mathbb{R}^n : |V^{-1}\varepsilon| \leq \chi_H\} \quad (27)$$

By applying Theorem 1 of (Kofman et al., 2007) to the dynamical system described by (14) and (15) satisfying (19), we can prove that $\Omega_H(\infty)$ is also robust positively invariant (RPI), which implies that if $\varepsilon_{x_H}(0) \in \Omega_H(\infty)$, then $\varepsilon_{x_H}(t) \in \Omega_H(\infty)$ for all $t > 0$ ($\varepsilon_{x_H}(t)$ may converge to $\Omega_H(\infty)$ in finite time and not only asymptotically). Here, if $|V^{-1}\bar{x}| \leq \chi_H$, then $\varepsilon_{x_H}(0) \in \Omega_H(\infty)$ for all $t \geq 0$.

Based on (23) and (24), at every time instant $\varepsilon_{y_H}(t)$ resides within a set $\mathcal{P}_H(t)$ defined as

$$\mathcal{P}_H(t) = \{\varepsilon \in \mathbb{R}^m : |\varepsilon| \leq \bar{\varepsilon}_y(t)\} \quad (28)$$

$\mathcal{P}_H(t)$ is an orthotope which converges to the limit set, denoted by $\mathcal{P}_H(\infty)$, associated with the RPI set $\Omega_H(\infty)$; i.e.

$$\varepsilon_{y_H}(\infty) \in \mathcal{P}_H(\infty) \quad (29)$$

$$\mathcal{P}_H(\infty) = \{\varepsilon \in \mathbb{R}^m : |\varepsilon| \leq \nu_H\} \quad (30)$$

$$\nu_H = C|V|\chi_H + \bar{d} \quad (31)$$

When $f(t) = 0$, the residual is guaranteed to reside within $\mathcal{P}_H(t)$ and to converge to the limit set $\mathcal{P}_H(\infty)$.

3.3 Fault Detection Decision Logic

At every time instant, we monitor the residual defined in (6) by checking whether $\varepsilon_y(t)$ lies in $\mathcal{P}_H(t)$. If there exists $t \geq T_i$ such that

$$\varepsilon_y(t) \notin \mathcal{P}_H(t) \quad (32)$$

then $f(t)$ is guaranteed to be detected. The time of fault detection is defined as $t_D = \inf\{t : \varepsilon_y(t) \notin \mathcal{P}_H(t)\}$.

4. PERFORMANCE INDEX BASED ON FAULT DETECTABILITY

This section deals with the design of a performance index that guarantees the detectability of the FD-scheme, taking into account sensor faults described by (3)-(5). The weak and strong detectability of permanent sensor faults are characterized as follows (Blanke et al., 2016):

Definition 1. A permanent sensor fault f_i is *weakly detectable* if its effects cause the residual $\varepsilon_y(t)$ to exit from $\mathcal{P}_H(t)$ and stay out of it for some $t \geq t_D > T_i$, i.e. (32) is valid for some $t \geq t_D > T_i$.

Definition 2. A permanent sensor fault f_i is *strongly detectable* if its effects cause the residual $\varepsilon_y(t)$ to exit from $\mathcal{P}_H(t)$ and stay out of it for all $t \geq t_D > T_i$, i.e. (32) is valid for all $t \geq t_D > T_i$.

Certain conditions that ensure the validity of (32) can be derived based on the behavior of the residual under the occurrence of a single permanent sensor fault. Since the residual generator is a dynamical system, we can compute the convex, closed set denoted by $\mathcal{P}(t)$ where $\varepsilon_y(t)$ is guaranteed to reside under faulty conditions; i.e.,

$$\varepsilon_y(t) \in \mathcal{P}(t), \forall t \geq T_i \quad (33)$$

Then the weak fault detectability is guaranteed if the conditions of Lemma 1 are satisfied for some $t > T_i$, while the strong fault detectability is guaranteed if these conditions are valid for all $t > T_i$.

Lemma 1. If $\mathcal{P}(t) \cap \mathcal{P}_H(t) = \emptyset$, then $\varepsilon_y(t) \notin \mathcal{P}_H(t)$ and (32) is valid.

Proof. Suppose that $\varepsilon_y(t) \in \mathcal{P}_H(t)$. Given (33), it yields $\varepsilon_y(t) \in \mathcal{P}(t) \cap \mathcal{P}_H(t)$. This contradicts our assumption that $\mathcal{P}(t) \cap \mathcal{P}_H(t) = \emptyset$. So $\varepsilon_y(t) \notin \mathcal{P}_H(t)$.

The design of $\mathcal{P}(t)$ is presented in Section 4.1. The sets $\mathcal{P}(t)$ and $\mathcal{P}_H(t)$ do not intersect iff their distance is positive, which is determined in Section 4.2.

4.1 Limit set of the residual generator under faulty conditions

The effects of sensor faults on the residual $\varepsilon_y(t)$ can be determined as

$$\varepsilon_{y_F}(t) = \varepsilon_y(t) - \varepsilon_{y_H}(t), \quad t \geq T_i \quad (34)$$

where ε_{y_H} is defined in (13). For $t \geq T_i$, \hat{x} satisfies

$$\dot{\hat{x}} = V\Lambda V^{-1}\hat{x} + \gamma(y_H + f, u) + L(y_H + f) \quad (35)$$

with y_H defined in (10). Based on (2) and (10) the residual is defined as

$$\varepsilon_y = y - C\hat{x} = y_H + f - C\hat{x} \quad (36)$$

By combining (13), (34) and (36), the sensor fault effects can be expressed as

$$\varepsilon_{y_F} = -C\varepsilon_{x_F} + f, \quad (37)$$

$$\varepsilon_{x_F} = \hat{x} - \hat{x}_H \quad (38)$$

where ε_{x_F} represents the sensor fault effects on the state estimation. For $t \geq T_i$, the fault function $\varphi_i(t)$ defined in (4), can be described by

$$\varphi_i(t) = \varphi_{0i} + \tilde{\varphi}_i(t), \quad (39)$$

where $\varphi_{0i} \in \mathbb{R}$ is the (unknown) non-zero offset and $\tilde{\varphi}_i(t) \in \mathbb{R}$ represents the deviation of $\varphi_i(t)$ from φ_{0i} . Based on Assumption 4, $\tilde{\varphi}_i(t)$ is assumed to be bounded; i.e.,

$$|\tilde{\varphi}_i(t)| \leq \bar{\varphi}_i, \quad \forall t \geq T_i \quad (40)$$

where $\bar{\varphi}_i \in \mathbb{R}$. By introducing (39) in (4), we obtain:

$$f_i(t) = f_{0i} + \tilde{f}_i(t), \quad \forall t \geq T_i \quad (41)$$

$$f_{0i} = \varphi_{0i} \quad (42)$$

$$\tilde{f}_i(t) = \left(1 - e^{-\alpha_i(t-T_i)}\right) \tilde{\varphi}_i(t - T_i) - \varphi_{0i}e^{-\alpha_i(t-T_i)} \quad (43)$$

Taking into account (40) we have

$$|\tilde{f}_i(t)| \leq \left(1 - e^{-\alpha_i(t-T_i)}\right) \bar{\varphi}_i + |\varphi_{0i}|e^{-\alpha_i(t-T_i)} = \bar{f}_i(t) \quad (44)$$

where the bound $\bar{f}_i(t)$ satisfies

$$\bar{f}_i(t) \leq |\varphi_{0i}| \quad (45)$$

Based on (39) and (40), $\varphi_i \in [-\bar{\varphi}_i + \varphi_{0i}, \bar{\varphi}_i + \varphi_{0i}]$. Since $\varphi_i(t) \neq 0, \forall t \geq 0$ then

$$|\varphi_{0i}| > \bar{\varphi}_i \quad (46)$$

While the bound in (45) is valid for all $t \geq T_i$ is rather conservative as time progresses, because it does not consider the exponential decay entailing that $\bar{f}_i(t) \rightarrow \bar{\varphi}_i$ as $t \rightarrow \infty$. A workaround to this problem is to pick any positive number δ_i such that $\bar{\varphi}_i < \bar{\varphi}_i + \delta_i \leq |\varphi_{0i}|$, resulting in

$$\bar{f}_i(t) \leq \bar{\varphi}_i + \delta_i, \quad \forall t \geq T_i + \tilde{t}(a_i, \delta_i, |\varphi_{0i}|) \quad (47)$$

$$\tilde{t}(a_i, \delta_i, |\varphi_{0i}|) = \frac{1}{a_i} \log \left(\frac{|\varphi_{0i}| - \bar{\varphi}_i}{\delta_i} \right) \quad (48)$$

Using (9), (11), (35) and (41), ε_{x_F} defined in (38) satisfies

$$V^{-1}\dot{\tilde{\varepsilon}}_{x_F} = \Lambda V^{-1}\tilde{\varepsilon}_{x_F} + z_f \quad (49)$$

$$z_f = V^{-1}(\gamma(y_H + \mathbb{F}^{(i)}\varphi_{0i} + \mathbb{F}^{(i)}\tilde{f}_i, u) - \gamma(y_H, u)) + (V^{-1}A - \Lambda V^{-1})C^\top \mathbb{F}^{(i)}\tilde{f}_i \quad (50)$$

$$\dot{\tilde{\varepsilon}}_{x_F}(t) = \varepsilon_{x_F}(t) + (V\Lambda^{-1}V^{-1}A - I)C^\top \mathbb{F}^{(i)}\varphi_{0i} \quad (51)$$

where $\mathbb{F}^{(i)}$ is defined in (5), $\varepsilon_{x_F}(T_i) = \hat{x}(T_i) - \hat{x}_H(T_i) = 0$ since $f_i(T_i) = 0$ according to (3), and

$$\tilde{\varepsilon}_{x_F}(T_i) = (V\Lambda^{-1}V^{-1}A - I)C^\top \mathbb{F}^{(i)}\varphi_{0i} \quad (52)$$

Taking into account Assumption 2 and (41)-(44), z_f satisfies

$$|z_f| \leq |V^{-1}|\Gamma|\varphi_{0i}| + \left(|V^{-1}|\Gamma + MC_i^\top\right)\tilde{f}_i(t), \quad \forall t \geq T_i \quad (53)$$

$$M = |\Lambda V^{-1} - V^{-1}A| \quad (54)$$

where C_i^\top is the i -th column of C^\top , $i \in \{1, \dots, m\}$. Based on (47) and (48), for all $t \geq T_i + \tilde{t}(a_i, \delta_i, |\varphi_{0i}|)$ z_f satisfies

$$|z_f| \leq |V^{-1}|\Gamma|\varphi_{0i}| + \left(|V^{-1}|\Gamma + MC_i^\top\right)(\bar{\varphi}_i + \delta_i) \quad (55)$$

The derivation of the bounds for $V^{-1}\tilde{\varepsilon}_{x_F}(t)$ are obtained next.

Lemma 2. If the eigenvalues Λ are real, negative, $\tilde{\varepsilon}_{x_F}$ defined in (49)-(51): (a) is uniformly bounded; i.e.

$$\tilde{\varepsilon}_{x_F}(t) \in \Omega_H(t), \quad \forall t \geq T_i \quad (56)$$

$$\Omega_F(t) = \{\varepsilon \in \mathbb{R}^n : |V^{-1}\varepsilon| \leq E_F(t)\} \quad (57)$$

where

$$E_F(t) = \chi_F + e^{\Lambda(t-T_i)} \left(\left| (\Lambda^{-1}V^{-1}A - V^{-1})C_i^\top \varphi_{0i} \right| - \chi_F \right) + H_2(t) \left(|V^{-1}|\Gamma + MC_i^\top \right) (|\varphi_{0i}| - \bar{\varphi}_i) \quad (58)$$

$$\chi_F = -\Lambda^{-1}(|V^{-1}|\Gamma(|\varphi_{0i}| + \bar{\varphi}_i) + MC_i^\top \bar{\varphi}_i) \quad (59)$$

$$H_2(t) = \text{diag}([H_{21}(t) \ H_{22}(t) \ \dots \ H_{2n}(t)]) \quad (60)$$

$$H_{2j}(t) = \begin{cases} -(\lambda_j + \alpha_j)^{-1} \left(e^{-\alpha_j(t-T_i)} - e^{\lambda_j(t-T_i)} \right), & \text{if } \lambda_j \neq -\alpha_j \\ e^{-\alpha_j(t-T_i)}(t - T_i), & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (61)$$

(b) converges to the minimal ultimate bound set $\Omega_F(\infty)$ as $t \rightarrow \infty$

$$\Omega_F(\infty) = \{\varepsilon \in \mathbb{R}^n : |V^{-1}\varepsilon| \leq \chi_F\} \quad (62)$$

and

(c) belongs to the RPI set $\bar{\Omega}_F$ for all $t \geq T_i + \tilde{t}(a_i, \delta_i, |\varphi_{0i}|)$ if $\tilde{\varepsilon}_{x_F}(T_i + \tilde{t}(a_i, \delta_i, |\varphi_{0i}|)) \in \bar{\Omega}_F$, where $\delta_i \in (0, |\varphi_{0i}| - \bar{\varphi}_i)$ and

$$\bar{\Omega}_F = \{\varepsilon \in \mathbb{R}^n : |V^{-1}\varepsilon| \leq \bar{E}_F\} \quad (63)$$

$$\bar{E}_F = \chi_F - \Lambda^{-1} \left(|V^{-1}|\Gamma + MC_i^\top \right) \delta_i \quad (64)$$

Proof. The proof is given in the Appendix.

Remark 1. In the case that f_i has an abrupt evolution which is modeled by setting $\alpha_i \rightarrow \infty$, $H_2(t)$ defined through (60) and (61) converges to zero. Moreover, $\tilde{t}(a_i, \delta_i, |\varphi_{0i}|)$ defined in (48) converges also to zero, implying that we can choose an arbitrarily small δ_i that can make the ultimate bound $\bar{\Omega}_F$ to be almost the same as the minimal ultimate bound set $\Omega_F(\infty)$. Also $\tilde{t}(a_i, \delta_i, |\varphi_{0i}|) \rightarrow 0$ implies that $\bar{f}_i(t)$ satisfies (47) almost just after T_i .

Taking into account (37), (41) and (51), we have

$$\dot{\tilde{\varepsilon}}_{y_F} = -C\dot{\tilde{\varepsilon}}_{x_F} + \mathbb{F}^{(i)}\tilde{f}_i \quad (65)$$

$$\tilde{\varepsilon}_{y_F} = \varepsilon_{y_F} - CV\Lambda^{-1}V^{-1}AC_i^\top \varphi_{0i} \quad (66)$$

Bounding (65) and using Lemma 2(a) results in

$$|\dot{\tilde{\varepsilon}}_{y_F}| \leq |CV|E_F(t) + \mathbb{F}^{(i)}\tilde{f}_i(t), \quad (67)$$

for all $t \geq T_i$ where E_F and $\mathbb{F}^{(i)}$ are defined in (58) and (5), respectively. According to (66) and (67), ε_{y_F} belongs to the time-varying set $\mathcal{P}_F(t) = \{\varepsilon \in \mathbb{R}^m : |\varepsilon - CV\Lambda^{-1}V^{-1}AC_i^\top \varphi_{0i}| \leq |CV|E_F + \mathbb{F}^{(i)}\tilde{f}_i(t)\}$ for all $t \geq T_i$. Taking into account (34), it yields that $\varepsilon_y(t) \in \mathcal{P}(t)$, where

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{P}(t) &= \{\mathcal{P}_H(t) \oplus \mathcal{P}_F(t)\} \\ &= \{\varepsilon \in \mathbb{R}^m : |\varepsilon - CV\Lambda^{-1}V^{-1}AC_i^\top \varphi_{0i}| \leq \mathbb{F}^{(i)} \bar{f}_i(t) + \bar{\varepsilon}_y(t) \\ &\quad + |CV|E_F(t)\}\end{aligned}\quad (68)$$

where $\mathcal{P}_H(t)$ is defined in (28).

Based on Lemma 2(b), as $t \rightarrow \infty$ it yields

$$|\tilde{\varepsilon}_{y_F}(\infty)| \leq |CV|\mathcal{X}_F + \mathbb{F}^{(i)}\bar{\varphi}_i = \nu_F \quad (69)$$

Consequently, ε_{y_F} converges asymptotically to the limit set $\mathcal{P}_F(\infty) = \{\varepsilon \in \mathbb{R}^m : |\varepsilon - CV\Lambda^{-1}V^{-1}AC_i^\top \varphi_{0i}| \leq \nu_F\}$, implying that $\varepsilon_y(t)$ asymptotically converges to $\mathcal{P}(\infty)$, defined as

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{P}(\infty) &= \{\mathcal{P}_H(\infty) \oplus \mathcal{P}_F(\infty)\} \\ &= \{\varepsilon \in \mathbb{R}^m : |\varepsilon - CV\Lambda^{-1}V^{-1}AC_i^\top \varphi_{0i}| \leq \nu_F + \nu_H\}\end{aligned}\quad (70)$$

Based on (47), (48) and Lemma 2(c), for all $t \geq T_i + \tilde{t}(a_i, \delta_i, |\varphi_{0i}|)$, $\tilde{\varepsilon}_{y_F}$ satisfies

$$|\tilde{\varepsilon}_{y_F}| \leq |CV|\bar{E}_F + \mathbb{F}^{(i)}\bar{\varphi}_i + \mathbb{F}^{(i)}\delta_i \quad (71)$$

where \bar{E}_F is given in (64). Then, ε_{y_F} belongs to the set $\bar{\mathcal{P}}_F = \{\varepsilon \in \mathbb{R}^m : |\varepsilon - CV\Lambda^{-1}V^{-1}AC_i^\top \varphi_{0i}| \leq \nu_F - |CV|\Lambda^{-1}(|V^{-1}|\Gamma + MC_i^\top)\delta_i + \mathbb{F}^{(i)}\delta_i\}$, for all $t \geq T_i + \tilde{t}(a_i, \delta_i, |\varphi_{0i}|)$ where ν_F is defined in (69). Thus, it yields $\varepsilon_y(t) \in \bar{\mathcal{P}}$, where

$$\begin{aligned}\bar{\mathcal{P}} &= \{\mathcal{P}_H(\infty) \oplus \bar{\mathcal{P}}_F\} \\ &= \{\varepsilon \in \mathbb{R}^m : |\varepsilon - CV\Lambda^{-1}V^{-1}AC_i^\top \varphi_{0i}| \leq \nu_F + \nu_H \\ &\quad - |CV|\Lambda^{-1}(|V^{-1}|\Gamma + MC_i^\top)\delta_i + \mathbb{F}^{(i)}\delta_i\}\end{aligned}\quad (72)$$

where $\mathcal{P}_H(\infty)$ is defined in (30). Note that $\mathcal{P}_H(\infty)$ and $\bar{\mathcal{P}}_F$ are associated with the RPI, ultimate bound sets $\Omega_H(\infty)$ and $\bar{\Omega}_F$ defined in (27) and (63), respectively.

Remark 2. The set \mathcal{P}_H is related to the robustness of the observer-based FD scheme described in Section 3 with respect to system disturbances and measurement noise, while \mathcal{P} is associated with its fault sensitivity under uncertainty.

4.2 Distance between Fault-Free and Faulty Limit Sets

As discussed at the beginning of Section 4, the weak detectability of the sensor fault f_i , $i \in \{1, \dots, m\}$ can be guaranteed if the distance between $\mathcal{P}(t)$ and $\mathcal{P}_H(t)$, denoted by $D(t)$, is positive. Given that \mathcal{P} and \mathcal{P}_H are nonzero- and zero-centered orthotopes respectively, we seek the distance between their orthogonal projections that is positive in at least one dimension and for at least one time instant; i.e.

$$D_q(t) = \text{dist}(\mathcal{P}_q(t), \mathcal{P}_{Hq}(t)) \quad (73)$$

$$D_q(t) > 0, \text{ for some } q \in \{1, \dots, m\} \& t \geq T_i \quad (74)$$

where $\mathcal{P}_q(t)$ and $\mathcal{P}_{Hq}(t)$ are the projections of $\mathcal{P}(t)$ and $\mathcal{P}_H(t)$ on the q -th axis respectively, defined as

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{P}_q(t) &= \left\{ \varepsilon \in \mathbb{R} : \varepsilon \in \left[-(\mathbb{F}_q^{(i)} \bar{f}_i(t) + C_q|V|E_F(t) + \bar{\varepsilon}_{y_q}(t)), \right. \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left. \mathbb{F}_q^{(i)} \bar{f}_i(t) + C_q|V|E_F(t) + \bar{\varepsilon}_{y_q}(t) \right] + c_q \right\}\end{aligned}\quad (75)$$

$$c_q = C_qV\Lambda^{-1}V^{-1}AC_i^\top \varphi_{0i} \quad (76)$$

$$\mathcal{P}_{Hq}(t) = \left\{ \varepsilon \in \mathbb{R} : \varepsilon \in \left[-\bar{\varepsilon}_{y_q}(t), \bar{\varepsilon}_{y_q}(t) \right] \right\} \quad (77)$$

where $\mathbb{F}_q^{(i)}\bar{\varphi}_i$ and $\bar{\varepsilon}_{y_q}$ are the q -th element of $\mathbb{F}^{(i)}\bar{\varphi}_i$ and $\bar{\varepsilon}_y$, respectively. Note that $\mathbb{F}_q^{(i)}\bar{\varphi}_i = 0$ for all $q \neq i$. Then the distance is defined as

$$D_q(t, V, \Lambda) = \left| C_qV\Lambda^{-1}V^{-1}AC_i^\top \varphi_{0i} \right| - 2\bar{\varepsilon}_{y_q}(t) - (\mathbb{F}_q^{(i)}\bar{f}_i(t) + C_q|V|E_F(t)) \quad (78)$$

The distance D_q is parameterized with respect to the design parameters of the residual and adaptive threshold generator and can be used to evaluate the weak detectability of the FD scheme with respect to various faults f_i . Though valuable, D_q is not suitable for optimizing the design of the FD scheme due to its dependence with time.

The strong detectability of the FD scheme with respect to the sensor fault f_i , $i \in \{1, \dots, m\}$ can be guaranteed if the distance between $\mathcal{P}(\infty)$ and $\mathcal{P}_H(\infty)$ is positive. Based on the definition of $\mathcal{P}_H(\infty)$ and $\mathcal{P}(\infty)$ given in (30) and (70) respectively, the projections on the q -th axis are defined as

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{P}_q(\infty) &= \left\{ \varepsilon \in \mathbb{R} : \varepsilon \in \left[-\nu_{Fq} - \nu_{Hq}, \nu_{Fq} + \nu_{Hq} \right] + c_q \right\} \\ \mathcal{P}_{Hq}(\infty) &= \left\{ \varepsilon \in \mathbb{R} : \varepsilon \in \left[-\nu_{Hq}, \nu_{Hq} \right] \right\}\end{aligned}\quad (79)$$

where ν_{Hq} and ν_{Fq} is the q -th element of ν_H and ν_F respectively. Thus, their distance denoted by D_q^∞ is defined as

$$D_q^\infty(V, \Lambda) = \left| C_qV\Lambda^{-1}V^{-1}AC_i^\top \varphi_{0i} \right| - 2\nu_{Hq} - \nu_{Fq} \quad (80)$$

The distance D_q^∞ does not depend on time; therefore it could be used for both the evaluation of the FD scheme with respect to strong detectability, and its optimization. By combining (69) with (59) and (31) with (20), (80) can be re-written as

$$D_q^\infty(V, \Lambda) = a_{1q}(V, \Lambda)|\varphi_{0i}| - a_{2q}(V, \Lambda)\bar{\varphi}_i - a_{3q}(V, \Lambda) \quad (81)$$

$$a_{1q}(V, \Lambda) = \left| C_qV\Lambda^{-1}V^{-1}AC_i^\top \right| - C_q|V||\Lambda^{-1}V^{-1}|\Gamma \quad (82)$$

$$\begin{aligned}a_{2q}(V, \Lambda) &= C_q|V||\Lambda^{-1}V^{-1}|\Gamma + C_q|V||V^{-1} - \Lambda^{-1}V^{-1}A|C_i^\top \\ &\quad + \mathbb{F}_q^{(i)}\end{aligned}\quad (83)$$

$$\begin{aligned}a_{3q}(V, \Lambda) &= 2C_q|V||V^{-1} - \Lambda^{-1}V^{-1}A|C_i^\top \bar{d} \\ &\quad + 2C_q|V||\Lambda^{-1}V^{-1}|(|\Gamma|\|\bar{d}\| + \bar{\eta}) + 2\bar{d}_q\end{aligned}\quad (84)$$

Given that $a_{2q}(V, \Lambda), a_{3q}(V, \Lambda), \bar{\varphi}_i > 0$, if $a_{1q}(V, \Lambda) \leq 0$, then it yields that $D_q^\infty(V, \Lambda) \leq 0$. Thus, the necessary condition to find a positive distance $D_q^\infty(V, \Lambda)$ is

$$a_{1q}(V, \Lambda) > 0 \quad (85)$$

By ensuring that $D_q^\infty > 0$, we guarantee the strong detectability of the FD scheme *asymptotically*. An alternative for ensuring strong detectability *in possibly finite time* is to guarantee the positiveness of the distance between the invariant sets $\mathcal{P}_H(\infty)$ and $\bar{\mathcal{P}}$, denoted by \bar{D}_q . Based on the definition $\bar{\mathcal{P}}$ given in (72), its projection on the q -th axis is defined as

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{P}_q(\infty) &= \left\{ \varepsilon \in \mathbb{R} : \varepsilon \in \left[-(\nu_{Fq} + \nu_{Hq} - C_q|V|\Lambda^{-1}(|V^{-1}|\Gamma + MC_i^\top)\delta_i + \mathbb{F}_q^{(i)}\delta_i), \right. \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left. \nu_{Fq} + \nu_{Hq} - C_q|V|\Lambda^{-1}(|V^{-1}|\Gamma + MC_i^\top)\delta_i + \mathbb{F}_q^{(i)}\delta_i \right] + c_q \right\}\end{aligned}\quad (86)$$

where $\mathbb{F}_q^{(i)}$ stands for the q -th element of $\mathbb{F}^{(i)}$ defined in (5). Taking into account (48), (79), (81)-(84) and (86), we have

$$\begin{aligned}\bar{D}_q(V, \Lambda) &= \left(a_{1q}(V, \Lambda) - a_{2q}(V, \Lambda)e^{-a_i\bar{t}} \right) |\varphi_{0i}| \\ &\quad - a_{2q}(V, \Lambda) \left(1 - e^{-a_i\bar{t}} \right) \bar{\varphi}_i - a_{3q}(V, \Lambda)\end{aligned}\quad (87)$$

Given that $a_{2q}(V, \Lambda), a_{3q}(V, \Lambda), \bar{\varphi}_i > 0$ and $1 - e^{-a_i\bar{t}} \geq 0$ (see (48)), if $a_{1q}(V, \Lambda) - a_{2q}(V, \Lambda)e^{-a_i\bar{t}} \leq 0$, then it yields that $\bar{D}_q(V, \Lambda) \leq 0$. Thus, the necessary condition to find a positive distance $\bar{D}_q(V, \Lambda)$ is

$$a_{1q}(V, \Lambda) - a_{2q}(V, \Lambda)e^{-a_i\bar{t}} > 0 \quad (88)$$

Fig. 1. The shaded area represents all the pairs $(|\varphi_{0i}|, \bar{\varphi}_i)$ ensuring that f_i is strongly detectable.

4.3 Formulation of the optimization problem

We first formulate the problem of finding the design parameters of the residual generator, described by (6) and (7), and the adaptive set $\mathcal{P}_H(t)$ defined in (28) given (20), (22) and (24) by maximizing the set of *asymptotically* strongly detectable faults.

Definition 3. The set of faults occurring in sensor i , $i \in \{1, \dots, m\}$ that are asymptotically strongly detectable is expressed as

$$\mathcal{F}_i^\infty(V, \Lambda) = \left\{ f_i(t) = (1 - e^{-\alpha_i(t-T_i)}) (\varphi_{0i} + \bar{\varphi}_i(t-T_i)) : |\bar{\varphi}_i(t)| \leq \bar{\varphi}_i < |\varphi_{0i}|, \right. \\ \left. \& D_q^\infty(V, \Lambda) > 0 \right\} \quad (89)$$

Based on the distance D_q^∞ defined through (81)-(84), for a specific design V, Λ , the offset magnitude $|\varphi_{0i}|$ and the variation bound $\bar{\varphi}_i$ of (asymptotically) strongly detectable faults f_i according to *Definition 3* lie in the shaded area of Fig. 1, which corresponds to the intersection between: (i) the area within the line S_{1q} and the horizontal axis (any point $(|\varphi_{0i}|, \bar{\varphi}_i)$ within this area satisfies $0 \leq \bar{\varphi}_i < |\varphi_{0i}|$), and (ii) the area below the line $S_{2q}(V, \Lambda)$ (any point $(|\varphi_{0i}|, \bar{\varphi}_i)$ within this area satisfies $D_q^\infty(V, \Lambda) > 0$). These lines are defined as

$$S_{1q} = \{ [|\varphi_{0i}|, \bar{\varphi}_i]^\top : |\varphi_{0i}| = \bar{\varphi}_i \} \quad (90)$$

$$S_{2q}(V, \Lambda) = \{ [|\varphi_{0i}|, \bar{\varphi}_i]^\top : a_{1q}(V, \Lambda)|\varphi_{0i}| - a_{2q}(V, \Lambda)\bar{\varphi}_i = a_{3q}(V, \Lambda) \} \quad (91)$$

and the indicated marks as

$$p_1 = \left(0, -\frac{a_{3q}(V, \Lambda)}{a_{2q}(V, \Lambda)} \right) \quad (92)$$

$$p_2 = \left(\frac{a_{3q}(V, \Lambda)}{a_{1q}(V, \Lambda)}, 0 \right) \quad (93)$$

$$p_3 = \left(\frac{a_{3q}(V, \Lambda)}{a_{1q}(V, \Lambda) - a_{2q}(V, \Lambda)}, \frac{a_{3q}(V, \Lambda)}{a_{1q}(V, \Lambda) - a_{2q}(V, \Lambda)} \right) \quad (94)$$

Given the validity of condition in (85), the set $\mathcal{F}_i^\infty(V, \Lambda)$ is maximized if the shaded area in Fig. 1 is *maximized*, that is if

- the critical point p_3 approaches zero when $a_{1q}(V, \Lambda) - a_{2q}(V, \Lambda) > 0$ (see Fig. 1(a))
- the critical point p_2 approaches zero when $a_{1q}(V, \Lambda) - a_{2q}(V, \Lambda) = 0$ (see Fig. 1(b))

- the critical point p_3 approaches $-\infty$ when $a_{1q}(V, \Lambda) - a_{2q}(V, \Lambda) < 0$ (see Fig. 1(c))

The shaded area is maximized if the coordinate of the critical point p_3 is minimized. Therefore, the optimization problem to maximize the set $\mathcal{F}_i^\infty(V, \Lambda)$ according to *Definition 3* is formulated as:

$$\max_{V^{(i)}, \Lambda^{(i)}} \frac{a_{1q}(V^{(i)}, \Lambda^{(i)}) - a_{2q}(V^{(i)}, \Lambda^{(i)}) + \mu}{a_{3q}(V^{(i)}, \Lambda^{(i)})} \quad (95a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } a_{1q}(V^{(i)}, \Lambda^{(i)}) > 0, \quad (95b)$$

where $V^{(i)}, \Lambda^{(i)}$ are associated with the sensor fault f_i , and a_{1q}, a_{2q}, a_{3q} are defined in (82)-(84). The constant μ is selected to be an arbitrary very small positive scalar and is used in order to discriminate solutions for which $a_{1q}(V^{(i)}, \Lambda^{(i)}) = a_{2q}(V^{(i)}, \Lambda^{(i)})$. In this case, the impact of $a_{3q}(V^{(i)}, \Lambda^{(i)})$ can be reflected on the objective function.

Similarly, we can formulate the problem of finding the design parameters Λ, V by maximizing the set of strongly detectable faults associated with the distance $\bar{D}_q(V, \Lambda)$ and defined as follows.

Definition 4. Given a value for \tilde{t} (see (48)), say \tilde{t}^* , the set of strongly detectable faults occurring in sensor i , $i \in \{1, \dots, m\}$ with evolution rate α_i^* is expressed as

$$\mathcal{F}_i(V, \Lambda) = \left\{ f_i(t) = (1 - e^{-\alpha_i(t-T_i)}) (\varphi_{0i} + \bar{\varphi}_i(t-T_i)) : |\bar{\varphi}_i(t)| \leq \bar{\varphi}_i < |\varphi_{0i}| \right. \\ \left. \& \alpha_i = \alpha_i^* \& \bar{D}_q(V, \Lambda) > 0 \forall t \geq T_i + \tilde{t}^* \right\} \quad (96)$$

The set $\mathcal{F}_i(V, \Lambda)$ is maximized if the shaded area of Fig. 1 is maximized, where the line $S_{2q}(V, \Lambda)$ is defined as

$$S_{2q}(V, \Lambda) = \left\{ [|\varphi_{0i}|, \bar{\varphi}_i]^\top : \left(a_{1q}(V, \Lambda) - a_{2q}(V, \Lambda)e^{-\alpha_i^* \tilde{t}^*} \right) |\varphi_{0i}| - a_{2q}(V, \Lambda)(1 - e^{-\alpha_i^* \tilde{t}^*}) \bar{\varphi}_i = a_{3q}(V, \Lambda) \right\} \quad (97)$$

and the critical points are

$$p_1 = \left(0, -\frac{a_{3q}(V, \Lambda)}{a_{2q}(V, \Lambda) - a_{2q}(V, \Lambda)e^{-\alpha_i^* \tilde{t}^*}} \right) \quad (98)$$

$$p_2 = \left(\frac{a_{3q}(V, \Lambda)}{a_{1q}(V, \Lambda) - a_{2q}(V, \Lambda)e^{-\alpha_i^* \tilde{t}^*}}, 0 \right) \quad (99)$$

and p_3 is the same as the one defined in (94). If we want to maximize the set $\mathcal{F}_i(V, \Lambda)$, the optimization problem is

formulated as the one shown in (95), where constraint (95b) is replaced by constraint (88).

5. CONCLUDING REMARKS

In this paper, we presented a new methodology for designing a performance index for an observer-based fault detection scheme that can be used to detect sensor faults in a class of nonlinear systems. The methodology was based on analyzing the weak and strong detectability of the fault detection scheme, taking into account incipient sensor faults. The proposed fault detection scheme consists of an observer-based residual generator and an adaptive threshold generator. Given that the residual generator is a dynamical system, we computed time-varying and invariant convex sets that guarantee the inclusion of the residual under fault-free and faulty conditions, based on the uniform and ultimate boundedness, as well as the robust positive invariance of the state estimation error. The novelty in the design of these sets stems from their parametrization with respect to the design parameters of the fault detection scheme, the bounds on the system disturbances and measurement noise, and the fault evolution rate and fault function. For evaluating the fault detection scheme, weak and strong detectability conditions are derived by guaranteeing the separation of the fault-free and faulty sets. For optimizing the design of fault detection scheme, the distance between the separated sets was utilized for defining the set of strongly detectable, incipient time varying sensor faults. The goal of the optimization problem was to find the design parameters of the fault detection scheme that maximize the set of strongly detectable sensor faults.

Future work will first involve the solution of the formulated optimization problems to maximize the set of strongly detectable abrupt and incipient faults, taking into account that the problem is nonlinear and non-convex. Among future goals will be to investigate the generalization of the research results (e.g. eigenstructure of the observer with complex eigenvalues, characterization of the set separation in the sense of Hausdorff distance) order to enable their applicability to other robust, observer-based fault detection schemes and characterize their performance.

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Appendix A. PROOF OF LEMMA 2

(a) The solution of (49) is

$$V^{-1}\tilde{\mathbf{e}}_{x_F} = e^{\Lambda(t-T_i)}V^{-1}\tilde{\mathbf{e}}_{x_F}(T_i) + \int_{T_i}^t e^{\Lambda(t-\tau)}z_f(\tau)d\tau \quad (\text{A.1})$$

where z_f is defined in (50). Bounding (A.1) results in

$$|V^{-1}\tilde{\mathbf{e}}_{x_F}| \leq e^{\Lambda(t-T_i)}|V^{-1}\tilde{\mathbf{e}}_{x_F}(T_i)| + \int_{T_i}^t e^{\Lambda(t-\tau)}|z_f(\tau)|d\tau \quad (\text{A.2})$$

Given (53) and (54), the integral in (A.2) satisfies the following equation

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{z}_f(t) &\succeq \int_{T_i}^t e^{\Lambda(t-\tau)}|z_f(\tau)|d\tau \\ \bar{z}_f(t) &= -\Lambda^{-1}(I - e^{\Lambda(t-T_i)})|V^{-1}|\Gamma|\varphi_{0i}| + H_1 \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.3})$$

$$H_1 = \int_{T_i}^t e^{\Lambda(t-\tau)}\left(|V^{-1}|\Gamma + MC_i^\top\right)\bar{f}_i(\tau)d\tau \quad (\text{A.4})$$

Based on (44), we have

$$\begin{aligned} H_1 &= -\Lambda^{-1}(I - e^{\Lambda(t-T_i)})\bar{\varphi}_i\left(|V^{-1}|\Gamma + MC_i^\top\right) \\ &\quad + H_2(t)(|\varphi_{0i}| - \bar{\varphi}_i)\left(|V^{-1}|\Gamma + MC_i^\top\right) \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.5})$$

$$H_2 = \int_{T_i}^t e^{\Lambda(t-\tau)}e^{-\alpha_i(\tau-T_i)}d\tau \quad (\text{A.6})$$

Since $e^{\Lambda t}$ is a diagonal matrix where each element equals to $e^{\lambda_j t}$, $j \in \{1, \dots, n\}$, then H_2 is defined in (60) with $H_{2j} = \int_{T_i}^t e^{\lambda_j(t-\tau)}e^{-\alpha_i(\tau-T_i)}d\tau$ given in (61). By introducing (A.5) in (A.3), we obtain

$$\bar{z}_f(t) = (I - e^{\Lambda(t-T_i)})\chi_F + H_2(t)(|\varphi_{0i}| - \bar{\varphi}_i)\left(|V^{-1}|\Gamma + MC_i^\top\right) \quad (\text{A.7})$$

with χ_F defined in (59). Combining (52), (A.2) and (A.7) results in $|V^{-1}\tilde{\mathbf{e}}_{x_F}(t)| \preceq E_F(t)$, where E_F is defined in (58).

(b) As $t \rightarrow \infty$, it yields $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} E_F(t) = \chi_F$, with E_F and χ_F respectively defined in (58) and (59).

(c) Taking into account (49) and (50), we have

$$V_j^{-1}\dot{\tilde{\mathbf{e}}}_{x_F} = \lambda_j V_j^{-1}\tilde{\mathbf{e}}_{x_F} + z_{f_j} \quad (\text{A.8})$$

$$\begin{aligned} z_{f_j} &= V_j^{-1}(\gamma(y_H + \mathbb{F}^{(i)}\varphi_{0i} + \mathbb{F}^{(i)}\bar{f}_i, u) - \gamma(y_H, u)) \\ &\quad + (V_j^{-1}A - \lambda_j V_j^{-1})\mathbb{F}^{(i)}\bar{f}_i \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.9})$$

where V_j^{-1} is the j -th row of V^{-1} and λ_j is the j -th diagonal element of Λ , for all $j \in \{1, \dots, n\}$. Let $\mathbf{v} = |V_j^{-1}\tilde{\mathbf{e}}_{x_F}|$; then for $V_j^{-1}\tilde{\mathbf{e}}_{x_F} \neq 0$,

$$\dot{\mathbf{v}} = \frac{\left(V_j^{-1}\tilde{\mathbf{e}}_{x_F}\right)\left(V_j^{-1}\dot{\tilde{\mathbf{e}}}_{x_F}\right)}{\left|V_j^{-1}\tilde{\mathbf{e}}_{x_F}\right|} = \lambda_j \mathbf{v} + \frac{\left(V_j^{-1}\tilde{\mathbf{e}}_{x_F}\right)z_{f_j}}{\left|V_j^{-1}\tilde{\mathbf{e}}_{x_F}\right|} \quad (\text{A.10})$$

Based on (55), it yields that for $t \geq T_i + \tilde{t}(a_i, \delta_i, |\varphi_{0i}|)$

$$\dot{\mathbf{v}} \leq \lambda_j \mathbf{v} + |V_j^{-1}|\Gamma|\varphi_{0i}| + \left(|V_j^{-1}|\Gamma + M_j C_i^\top\right)(\bar{\varphi}_i + \delta_i) \quad (\text{A.11})$$

Taking into account (59), (A.11) becomes

$$\dot{\mathbf{v}} \leq \lambda_j \mathbf{v} - \lambda_j \chi_{F_j} + \left(|V_j^{-1}|\Gamma + M_j C_i^\top\right)\delta_i \quad (\text{A.12})$$

For $V_j^{-1}\mathbf{e}_{x_F} = 0$, we utilize the upper-right hand derivative of \mathbf{v} (see Section 3.4 in (Khalil, 1996)), which satisfies $D^+\mathbf{v} \leq -\lambda_j \chi_{F_j} + \left(|V_j^{-1}|\Gamma + M_j C_i^\top\right)\delta_i$. Then for all $V_j^{-1}\mathbf{e}_{x_F}$,

$$D^+\mathbf{v} \leq \lambda_j \mathbf{v} - \lambda_j \chi_{F_j} + \left(|V_j^{-1}|\Gamma + M_j C_i^\top\right)\delta_i, \quad (\text{A.13})$$

for all $t \geq T_i + \tilde{t}(a_i, \delta_i, |\varphi_{0i}|)$ with $\mathbf{v}(T_i + \tilde{t}(a_i, \delta_i, |\varphi_{0i}|)) = |V_j^{-1}\tilde{\mathbf{e}}_{x_F}(T_i + \tilde{t}(a_i, \delta_i, |\varphi_{0i}|))|$. Let us define as w the solution of $\dot{w} = \lambda_j w - \lambda_j \chi_{F_j} + \left(|V_j^{-1}|\Gamma + M_j C_i^\top\right)\delta_i$, $\forall t \geq T_i + \tilde{t}(a_i, \delta_i, |\varphi_{0i}|)$ (A.14)

with $w(T_i + \tilde{t}(a_i, \delta_i, |\varphi_{0i}|)) = |V_j^{-1}\tilde{\mathbf{e}}_{x_F}(T_i + \tilde{t}(a_i, \delta_i, |\varphi_{0i}|))|$. Then, w is described by

$$\begin{aligned} w &= e^{\lambda_j(t-T_i-\tilde{t}(a_i, \delta_i, |\varphi_{0i}|))}\left(|V_j^{-1}\tilde{\mathbf{e}}_{x_F}(T_i + \tilde{t}(a_i, \delta_i, |\varphi_{0i}|))\right) - \chi_{F_j} \\ &\quad + \lambda_j^{-1}\left(|V_j^{-1}|\Gamma + M_j C_i^\top\right)\delta_i + \chi_{F_j} - \lambda_j^{-1}\left(|V_j^{-1}|\Gamma + M_j C_i^\top\right)\delta_i \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.15})$$

Applying comparison lemma (Khalil, 1996) to (A.13) and (A.14) results in

$$|V_j^{-1}\tilde{\mathbf{e}}_{x_F}(t)| \leq w(t) \quad (\text{A.16})$$

If $|V_j^{-1}\tilde{\mathbf{e}}_{x_F}(T_i + \tilde{t}(a_i, \delta_i, |\varphi_{0i}|))| \leq \chi_{F_j} - \lambda_j^{-1}\left(|V_j^{-1}|\Gamma + M_j C_i^\top\right)\delta_i$, then

$$|V_j^{-1}\tilde{\mathbf{e}}_{x_F}(t)| \leq \chi_{F_j} - \lambda_j^{-1}\left(|V_j^{-1}|\Gamma + M_j C_i^\top\right)\delta_i \quad (\text{A.17})$$

Since (A.17) is valid for all $j \in \{1, \dots, n\}$, it yields $|V^{-1}\tilde{\mathbf{e}}_{x_F}| \leq \bar{E}_F$ (\bar{E}_F is defined in (64)), which is valid for all $t \geq T_i + \tilde{t}(a_i, \delta_i, |\varphi_{0i}|)$.